

EFFECT OF ELECTROPLATING PARAMETERS ON MICROSTRUCTURE OF COPPER COATING ON CARBON FIBERS USED FOR FABRICATION OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In order to fabricate the high quality carbon fiber-reinforced aluminum matrix composite, a simple and effective electroplating technology was used to prepare the Cu coating on the carbon fibers. The effect of electroplating parameters on the quality of copper coating was characterized by scanning electron microscope observation and X-ray diffractometer analysis. The results indicated: with the help of electroplating additives, the Cu coating with fine grains can be continuously and uniformly deposited on the carbon fibers; an appropriate current density should be chosen to make a good Cu coating with suitable thickness; the coating thickness increases with the increase of plating time, but not linearly; the PH value is also an important factor which affect the smoothness and crystallite size of Cu coating on the carbon fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to its high specific strength, high specific modulus, high thermal and electric conductivity as well as low coefficient of thermal expansion, carbon fibers (CFs) have been widely used to reinforce different composites, such as metal-based composite, ceramic-based composite and plastic-based composite [1-4]. However, as the reinforcement of aluminum-based composite, the critical issues are the poor wettability and chemical reaction between CFs and aluminum (Al) matrix. The poor wettability would result in the difficult for the infiltration of aluminum into the intra-bundle area of carbon fibers; the reaction between CFs and aluminum would damage the carbon fibers. Both issues would affect the mechanical properties of final carbon fiber-reinforced aluminum composites (CFRAC). Thus, the fabrication of an appropriate coating on the carbon fibers is quite necessary for improving the wettability and inhibiting the interfacial reaction between aluminum and CFs [5, 6].

A great effort has been made to develop the coating technology on carbon fibers. Generally, CFs with metal and ceramic coatings are often used to reinforce the aluminum matrix composites [7-9]. Hajjari et al. [7] found that the nickel (Ni) coating on the CFs by chemical plating can significantly improve the tensile strength of aluminum composite. The high tensile strength could be attributed to the improved wettability and reduced reaction between CFs and Al during the fabrication process. However, another problem was arisen from the Ni solution in Al matrix during processing. Ni element from coating dissolved in Al matrix and formed the NiAl₃ metallic compound, which made the composite more brittle and finally weaken the strength of composite [8]. Tang et al. [9] deposited α -Al₂O₃ coating on short carbon fibers by sol-gel technology. The results were encouraging and showed that the formation of Al₄C₃ at the interface between Al matrix and short carbon fibers was refrained by the α -Al₂O₃ coating. The problem is that the sol-gel process is expensive and complex to fabricate the Al₂O₃ coating on the surface of CFs. It was found that copper (Cu) is more suitable as a coating material for the fabrication of CFRAC because of its good compatibility with Al matrix and high fiber-matrix interfacial bonding strength [8].

Compared with chemical plating and sol-gel coating technology, electroplating is a simple and

inexpensive technology, and has a weak impact on the environment [10]. In this work, in order to fabricate the high quality CFRAC, the electroplating technology was used to deposit a Cu coating on the carbon fibers. To obtain a high quality Cu coating, the effect of electroplating parameters (plating additive, plating current density, plating time and PH value) on the microstructure of copper coating was investigated, where the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used to characterize the microstructure and morphology of the Cu coating. X-ray Diffractometer (XRD) was utilized to characterize the consisting phase and measure the crystallite size of Cu coating.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

Commercially available PAN-based CFs (T-300, supplied by Toray Company, Japan) were used as the substrate. Acid copper electroplating solution was used as the Cu source for the deposition of Cu coating on the CFs. The electroplating solution mainly included pentahydrate copper sulphate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), copper chloride (CuCl_2), bis-(3-sulfopropyl disulfide) (SPS) and emulsifier OP-10. The CuCl_2 , SPS and OP-10 were the plating additives to improve the quality of Cu coating. Before the electroplating, the sizing on the surface of CFs was removed by a pretreatment to improve the wettability and electrical conductivity of CFs with the electroplating solution.

2.2 Preparation of Cu-coated CF

Quantitative reagents were dissolved in distilled water. And then they were mechanically stirred for 30 min to make a homogeneous electroplating solution. During the electroplating process, the pretreated CFs acted the cathode and placed between two Cu anodes in the electroplating bath as shown in Fig. 1. To start the deposition of Cu coating on the surfaces of CFs, the steady current was supplied to the Cu anodes and the CF cathode. With controlled current and time, the Cu coating with different thickness and morphologies could be deposited on the surfaces of CFs. After finishing the electroplating process, the Cu-coated CFs were cleaned with distilled water in an ultrasonic bath. Finally, the CFs with Cu coating were dried in a vacuum flask at room temperature and used for various analyses and tests.

Fig 1: The experiment setup used for the electroplating of Cu coating on CFs.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) with Energy Dispersive Spectrum (EDS) was used to characterize the morphology and consisting element of the Cu coating on carbon fibers. The consisting phase and crystallite size of coating were characterized by means of the X-ray Diffractometer (XRD).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of plating additives on the morphology of Cu coating

In order to know the effect of plating additives on the microstructure and morphology of Cu coating on the CFs, two kinds of electroplating solutions were used, namely the electroplating solutions with and without CuCl₂, SPS and OP-10.

Fig. 2 shows the microstructures and morphologies of fibers with different electroplating conditions observed by SEM. From Fig. 2(a), it was found that the surfaces of fibers without Cu coating characterized by many gullies, which were almost parallel to the axis of carbon fibers. The gullies might be formed during the fiber fabrication process. Actually, the surface of the as-received fibers normally was covered by the sizing. Due to the appearance of sizing, the surface of the as-received fibers are smoother than that of fibers used for electroplating. As we mentioned in section 2.1, the pretreatment could effectively remove the surface sizing on the fibers. After removing the sizing, the true surface of fibers was completely exposed to outside. The pretreatment might enhance the electroplating of Cu coating and the bonding strength between Cu coating and CFs. Fig. 2(b) shows the surface morphology of Cu-coated CFs, which was electroplated in the solution without additives (the electroplating condition: concentration of copper sulfate, 120 g/L; PH, 0.5; current density, 5 A/dm²; plating time, 6 min). From Fig. 2(b), it can be seen that fibers present a uniform diameter after electroplating, but the surfaces of fibers become very rough. And also some huge Cu particles are sitting on the surface of CFs. From the cross section image of Cu-coated fiber as shown in Fig. 2(c), it can be seen that the Cu was homogeneously electroplated on the surface of carbon fibers and presented a particle structure.

After using the additives, a smooth and uniform Cu coating can be obtained as shown in Fig. 2(d). It can be seen that the coatings are continuous and firmly adhere to CFs. It seems that the Cu particles in the coating are very fine. Comparing the Fig. 2(b) and (d), it was found that the quality of Cu coating was significantly affected by the additives to a great extent.

In the electroplating solution with additives, the different additives play the different role on the quality of Cu coating on CFs.

CuCl₂ plays an important role on the activation of Cu anodes, besides being used as a conductive additive in electroplating solution. CuCl₂ can generate Cl⁻ in the electroplating solution. Cl⁻ can inhibit the production of O₂ which can oxidize Cu⁺ to form the insoluble Cu₂O. Cu₂O can deposit on both Cu anodes and CF cathode. If Cu₂O deposited on the Cu anodes, which can prevent Cu from dissolving and finally leading to electroplating process is compelled to stop. If Cu and Cu₂O co-deposited on the CFs, which would increase the internal stress of coating and decrease the brightness, resulting in a rough coating surface. It was found that the solution containing copper sulfate and copper chloride can work efficiently. SPS acted as a brightener can adsorb on the surface of CF cathode and enlarge the electrochemical polarization of CF cathode, which would make the grain size of Cu is fine in the coating. On the other hand, the SPS can smoother the surface of coating and make the coating becoming shiny. OP-10 can reduce the surface tension stress between electrode and electroplating solution. And the co-existence of SPS and OP-10 can efficiently improve the smoothness of Cu coating [11, 12]. Furthermore, During the electroplating process, H⁺ was reduced to form H₂ on the cathode, and the H₂ bubbles can be adsorbed on the surface of CF cathode being acted as a barrier, which stop the deposition of Cu on CFs. OP-10 can adsorb on CFs and decrease the surface energy between CFs and solution, and making the H₂ bubbles is hardly adsorbed on CFs. Thus, a perfect Cu coating can be deposited on CFs.

Without the electroplating additives, it is difficult to deposit a high quality Cu coating on the CFs as shown in Fig. 2(b)-(c). With the electroplating additives, the Cu coating can be continuously and uniformly deposited on the CFs as show in Fig. 2(d).

Fig 2: Morphologies of the uncoated CFs and Cu-coated CFs observed by SEM: (a) uncoated CFs; (b) Cu-coated CFs without additives; (c) cross section of Cu-coated CFs without additives; (d) Cu-coated CFs with additives.

Fig 3: XRD patterns for the as-received CF and the Cu-coated CF.

Fig. 3 shows the XRD patterns for the as-received CFs and the Cu-coated CFs. The broadening of carbon peak might be caused by the low graphitization of carbon fibers. For the as-received CFs, there is no presence of Cu peaks, but three sharp diffraction peaks ((111), (200), (220)) of Cu in the Cu-coated CFs were clearly observed. It confirmed that the coatings are mainly composed of the Cu phase.

3.2 Effect of current density on the quality of Cu coating

To know the effect of current density on the quality of Cu coating on CFs, the Cu coatings were electroplated on CFs under varied current densities. Fig. 4 shows the morphologies of Cu-coated CFs under different current densities (electroplating condition: concentration of copper sulfate, 120 g/L; PH value, 0.5; plating time, 5 min). The current density was set to be 1 A/dm², 5 A/dm² and 9 A/dm², respectively. From Fig. 4(a), it was clear that many areas on CFs were not coated by copper. This means that continuous Cu coatings were difficult to be deposited on CFs at 1A/dm². This is due to that the low current density would result in the low migration rate of Cu²⁺ to the CF cathode. Thus, the low deposition rate can not make a uniform coating on CFs. However, at the current density of 5 A/dm², the Cu coatings on the CFs were very uniform and smooth as shown in Fig. 4(b). Even looking at them by eyes, the coated fibers in a fiber bundle were also separated each other, and presented a high brightness. In the case of 9 A/dm², the coating thickness seems very large. Due to the large current density resulting in a high deposition rate, sometimes, a few carbon fibers were stuck each other or packed together by plated Cu coating as shown in Fig. 4(c). In this case, the coated fibers are not suitable for the infiltration of metal matrix. Therefore, an appropriate current density should be chosen to make a good Cu coating with suitable thickness.

Fig 4: SEM images of Cu-coated CFs under different current densities: (a) 1 A/dm²; (b) 5 A/dm²; (c) 9 A/dm².

3.3 Effect of plating time on the quality of Cu coating

To know the effect of plating time on the quality of Cu coating on CFs, the Cu coatings were electroplated on CFs with different plating times. Fig.5 shows the effect of plating time on the quality of Cu coatings on CFs with varied plating times (electroplating condition: concentration of copper sulfate, 120 g/L; current density, 5 A/dm²; PH value, 0.5).

Fig. 5(a) shows the typical cross section image of Cu-coated CF with a plating time of 5 min. Based on the SEM observation, the thickness of Cu coating is about 2.5 μm. Fig. 5(b) shows the coating thickness as a function of plating time. From Fig. 5(b), it can be seen that the coating thickness was not linearly increased with increasing the plating time. When the plating time was longer than 11 min, the deposition rate of Cu became slow, which can be explained by the step kinematics theory, i.e., the copper deposited on CFs were formed by many microscopic steps and the distribution of these microscopic steps on CFs is uneven [13, 14].

Fig 5: Effect of plating time on the quality of Cu coating: (a) cross section of Cu-coated CFs with a plating time of 5 min; (b) the thickness of Cu coating as a function of plating time.

3.4 Effect of PH value on the quality of Cu coating

Fig. 6 shows the morphologies of Cu-coated CFs deposited under different PH values (electroplating condition: concentration of copper sulfate, 120 g/L; plating time, 5 min; current density, 5 A/dm²). By comparing the morphological features from the SEM observation, it was found that the PH value has a significant influence on the morphology of Cu coating. Fig. 6(a) shows the morphology of Cu-coating with a PH value of 0.9. It can be seen that the coatings are continuous and uniform. However, the surface is rough and shows a clear granular structure. Some defects can also be observed occasionally. When the PH value was decreased from 0.9 to 0.5, it was found that the thickness of coating layer is quite uniform and the coating surface shows a smooth and fine-grain structure as shown in Fig. 6(b). And also, there were no defects was found on the surface of coating (see Fig. 6(b)).

Fig. 6(c) shows the XRD patterns for the Cu-coated CFs under different PH values. Based on the characteristic peaks from the XRD patterns, a quantitative analysis for crystallite size of Cu coating was carried out by using the Scherrer formula [15]:

$$\beta \cos \theta = K(\lambda / d) \quad (1)$$

Where β is the value of FWHM (Full width at Half Maximum), θ Bragg angle, $K=0.94$ is the shape factor, λ wavelength for Cu K α radiation and d crystallite size.

The measured crystallite size from the diffraction peaks is not the real grain size, but it can be used as the reference for relative comparison of the grain size. In this work, the crystallite size was measured by using the FWHM from (111) diffraction peak according to the Eq. (1).

Fig. 6(d) shows the crystallite sizes of Cu coatings electroplated under different PH values. It can be seen that the low PH value (0.3) and high PH value (0.9) led to a large crystallite size (larger than 34 nm). When $\text{pH} < 3.0$, cathode current efficiency is fairly low, H_2 was generated, and Cu is difficult to be deposited on CFs. When the PH value varied from 0.5 to 0.7, the crystallite size is smaller than 30 nm. This indicated that the grain size is associated with the PH value. In order to understand PH value related grain growth mechanism, following mechanism was proposed. For the low PH value, it was easy to produce large amount of H_2 , which will be adsorbed on the CFs cathode. In the areas where H_2 bubbles adsorbed, the Cu nucleus can't be formed on the surfaces of CFs. But in the areas where no H_2 bubbles adsorbed, there were easily formed large Cu crystals, resulting in a rough surface and porous structure of Cu coating. When the PH value was high, it is easy to produce $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$. $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ can be adsorbed on the surfaces of Cu grains, and finally resulted in a granular structure of Cu coatings. On the other hand, the adsorbed $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ would refrain the release of the H_2 bubbles adsorbed on the CFs, leading to the Cu accumulation and the formation of defects as shown in Fig. 6(a).

Fig 6: Effect of PH value on the quality of Cu coating: (a) the morphology of Cu coating on CFs under $\text{PH}=0.9$; (b) the morphology of Cu coating on CFs under $\text{PH}=0.5$; (c) XRD patterns for Cu-coated CF with different PH values; (d) the crystallite size for Cu coatings electroplated under different PH values.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the current work, in order to fabricate the high quality carbon fiber-reinforced aluminum matrix composite, a simple and effective electroplating technology was used to prepare the Cu coating on the carbon fibers. To obtain a good quality of Cu coating, the effect of electroplating parameters on the microstructure of copper coating was investigated. The SEM was used to characterize the microstructure and morphology of the Cu coating. The XRD was used to characterize the consisting phase and measure the crystallite size of Cu coating. The main results are summarized as follows:

- (1) The quality of Cu coating was significantly affected by the additives to a great extent. Without the electroplating additives, it is difficult to deposit a high quality Cu coating on the CFs. In contrast, after using the electroplating additives, the Cu coating with fine grains can be continuously and uniformly deposited on the CFs.
- (2) The low current density would result in the low migration rate of Cu^{2+} on the CF cathode. Thus, the deposition rate of Cu is low on the CFs. At the current density of 5 A/dm^2 , the Cu coatings on the CFs are very uniform and smooth as shown in Fig. 3(b). High current density leading to a high deposition rate being stuck or packed fibers in a bundle, which is harmful for the infiltration of aluminum matrix. Therefore, an appropriate current density should be chosen to make a good Cu coating with suitable thickness.
- (3) It is found that the coating thickness increases with the increase of plating time. But when the plating time was longer than 11 min, the deposition rate of Cu became slow.
- (4) By comparing the morphological features from the SEM observation, it is found that the PH value has a significant influence on the morphology of Cu coating. When the PH value is ranging from 0.5 to 0.7, the thickness of coating layer is quite uniform and the coating surface shows a smooth and fine-grain structure.

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